

Research and Finding Credible Sources Scavenger Hunt GIFT

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Abstract

This GIFT activity presents a gamified approach to strengthening research literacy and oral citation skills in a basic or introductory communication course. The lesson engages students through a two-level scavenger hunt that requires locating credible sources, crafting accurate oral citations, and applying research tools such as library databases, Google Scholar, and Google News. By scaffolding instruction and aligning it with typical speech rubric criteria, the activity reinforces information literacy, ethical citation practices, and credibility judgments. Gamification increases motivation, engagement, and participation, while the verification process ensures instructional clarity and reinforces accuracy. Preliminary implementation across multiple course sections demonstrated measurable improvement in students' ability to locate, evaluate, and cite evidence orally during speeches. The activity also revealed students' increased confidence in research practices and ethical source integration. This adaptable design is transferable to online, hybrid, or discipline-specific contexts, making it a versatile tool for supporting foundational communication competencies.

Keywords: information literacy, gamification, oral citations, credibility.

The purpose of this lesson is to strengthen information literacy in students by providing hands-on opportunities to find, evaluate, and cite sources. Specifically, this activity developed to be used in a basic communication course (BCC) to help students improve their research and oral citation skills for speech assignments. This activity allows students to apply ethical standards associated with research, credibility, and public speaking and helps ensure students are equipped with these essential skills early in their academic careers. By the end of this process, students will be able to locate and evaluate credible sources relevant to their speech topics, integrate and orally cite supporting evidence appropriately, apply ethical standards when selecting, paraphrasing, and presenting research material, and assess the credibility of their sources.

This lesson serves as a formative step that scaffolds students' performance on major speech assignments. By aligning the learning outcomes, classroom activities, and grading criteria used in a typical BCC speech rubric, the lesson ensures that information literacy and ethical and accurate citation practices are taught, practiced, and assessed. More specifically, during major speech assignments, students are typically expected to be able to incorporate at least three credible oral citations, and their ability to do this effectively is generally demonstrated within the "Body" section of the speech rubric, which is typically worth 25-30% of their total speech grade.

To ensure consistency and transparency in evaluating oral citations and credibility judgments, the lesson uses a two-level plan aligned with the speech rubrics used for assessment in the course. During the first level of this process, students will demonstrate initial competence in locating credible sources and orally citing them properly. Feedback is formative, emphasizing accuracy of citation format and recognition of credible evidence. The next level asks students to apply their research skills again by using various research tools, such as their school's library database, Google Scholar, Google News, and more. Since students will engage with these processes during their graded major speech assignments, their oral citations and research worksheet are checked for accuracy by the instructor, and students will not advance levels until they have fully completed each step accurately and appropriately. In other words, this lesson provides teachers and students with the ability to achieve full clarity of the research expectations related to the major speech assignments in the course.

Rationale

College students are regularly expected to showcase their research skills by identifying relevant information from a variety of sources to showcase their information literacy (Cutillas et al., 2023). Consequently, it is imperative that teachers of the BCC do their best to help encourage the

development of research skills in their students. More specifically, during a BCC students are generally asked to utilize their research skills to develop quality oral citations. Oral citations are the result of the process of accumulating information on a topic from outside sources and reporting it to others during an oral presentation (Billington & McKay, 2022). Oral citations typically include the name of the author(s), the source's credentials/credibility, the date of publication, and any other relevant source information (Billington & McKay, 2022). Subjective teacher preferences can influence the teaching of oral citations, but these specific lessons can assist in the generation of more quality and complete citations from students (Buerkle & Gearhart, 2016). The process of properly citing sources orally during a formal speech presentation helps increase student information literacy and avoid plagiarism while boosting the credibility and ethos of the speaker.

For clarity, an example oral citation can sound similar to, "According to a 2020 article in the Journal of Learning, a reputable journal who publishes studies focused on the education of college students, 75% of students dislike public speaking (Grand Valley State University Speech Lab, 2024). This brief example contains the author name, source credentials, date of publication, and the information being used to support a claim. Another example, which is utilized in this lesson plan, is citing the popular song "See You Again" by musical artist, Wiz Khalifa. This oral citation could sound like, "According to the rapper, Wiz Khalifa, a highly successful, Grammy nominated rapper, in his 2015 song, "See You Again" played at the end of the movie, Furious 7, the lyrics state, 'We've come a long way from where we began and I'll tell you all about it when I see you again.'" The previously mentioned examples include the necessary components of an oral citation, which are, author name, author credibility, date of publication, and other relevant source information.

During a BCC, oral citations and conducting quality research have been found to be one of the most difficult aspects of the speech development process for students (Kinnick & Holler, 2012). Some possible reasons for this struggle can be due to university librarians struggling to target literacy instruction to students who need it most (LeMire et al., 2025), significant gaps among students' research skills (Dempsey & Dalrymple, 2023), and because of the rise of a reliance on A.I., which some define as a disruptive force on the education system (Yu & Guo, 2023).

Since improving the research and information literacy skills of students is essential, BCC teachers should be certain that information literacy skills are clearly addressed in their courses. To ensure these skills are developed, this research-focused activity utilizes gamification. Gamification is defined as adding game-like features to nongame contexts (Rahmi et al., 2025). Within the context of education, gamification has been found to increase students' concentration, motivation, engagement, and increase student outcomes (Celasun & Kaya, 2025; Oliveira et al., 2022). Compared to traditional teaching, gamification has the potential to yield a variety of positive student outcomes such as teachers creating a more enjoyable learning experience, encouraging students to develop a more positive attitude toward learning, increased student motivation, increased in information literacy skills,

and a significant increase in student performance (Wang et al., 2024). The elements of gamification, which are utilized in this research focused activity, cultivate a sense of achievement and progression, which has been found to drive students to engage more deeply with the material and develop these skills more effectively (Celasun & Kaya, 2025). Gamification elements have the ability to reveal significant effects on both the cognitive factors and affective dimensions of students, including motivation, participation, and academic achievement (Simsek & Karakus Yilmaz, 2025). The development and implementation of this activity capitalizes on the advantages of gamification to ensure that students are developing high quality oral citations and cultivating quality research habits. The positive outcomes associated with the utilization of gamification in the classroom have the ability to overcome the previously mentioned significant gaps in students' research abilities.

Explanation of Activity

After covering the textbook materials related to conducting quality research and citing sources, teachers will then separate students into small groups and prepare to facilitate the activity. Due to the incorporation of gamification, this activity contains two levels and students must complete the first level before moving on to the next. The first level asks students to find specific sources and cite them correctly. The second level asks students to complete a research focused worksheet where they will need to utilize a variety of research tools.

Logistics and Materials

This lesson and activity typically need 90 minutes to 2 hours to complete in a class with approximately 20-25 students. Instructors will need to print out additional "scavenger hunt" worksheets prior to the start of class. A PowerPoint or Google Slides presentation should also be created and projected to facilitate the activity. Therefore, instructors should have a preparation checklist consisting of the following: fully developed slides, printed worksheets, access to an overhead projector, and the necessary time needed for students to complete this lesson and activity.

Directions

The specific process of this activity involves teachers presenting the clues to the students, 30 seconds per clue. Clues are presented from vague to specific to provide guided direction during the research process. This part of the activity contains 5 total movie clues, including popular films like The Matrix, Furious 7, Perks of Being a Wallflower, and more, all of which have famous scenes including famous songs. Instructors can include, omit, or change the movie/song/example at their leisure. Engaging in this process allows students to enhance the efficiency of their research practices, explore different research tools, and craft accurate oral citations that support their work throughout the course.

Students complete this level once accurate oral citations have been created for each movie/song referenced. Each round dedicated to movie clues will take approximately 5-10 minutes. Students will use clues to research the corresponding movie, then find the corresponding song, and create an accurate oral citation. Prior to starting the process, instructors

should clearly explain the directions for this activity should be stated clearly to students. The directions presented on the slides in class should resemble the process below.

- Use the clues AND YOUR RESEARCH SKILLS to find the MOVIE being described.
- Once the movie is found, find the artist and title of the SONG used in the movie's corresponding scene.
- Once the song is found, cite it correctly using each component of oral citation.
- The round is completed once the ARTIST AND SONG are cited correctly.
- Do not shout out answers. Ask for verification.
- Once verified, the level is complete.

Due to the succinctness of these directions, a few of these steps require more discussion. Specifically, if students shout out answers, teachers reserve the right to disqualify those students for that round. However, students complete this specific part of the process when they have successfully generated an accurate oral citation. So, shouting answers is not recommended mainly because it negatively impacts the student's ability to "win" the round and finish first among their classmates. Instructors may also choose to award extra credit to students who are the first to produce an accurate citation.

The primary focus for teachers during the movie clue level is the verification process. During this portion of the activity, instructors will meet with each group or individual student to confirm the accuracy of their citations. Instructors will review all student-created oral citations and provide immediate feedback to correct any observed errors. This collaborative process allows both instructors and students to clarify concepts and reinforce accurate citation practices. Additionally, the slideshow teachers develop should include correct examples that serve as reference points, ensuring that students can compare their work and address any lingering confusion after each round. Again, instructors may also choose to award extra credit to students who complete accurate citations most quickly. The competitive element of this approach, which is common during the inclusion of gamification in the classroom, can enhance student engagement and motivation. Even when implementing the strategy of encouraging speediness, instructors will still circulate throughout the classroom to discuss student responses and provide individualized feedback. Figures below present screenshots illustrating the full movie clue process using Google Slides.

Example: We are doing this together

- Clues
 1. Movie stars Brad Pitt
 - Make short list of movies with him (potential sources)
 - Search his IMDB.
 2. This song very famously plays during the outro of the movie
 - Google "songs at end of Brad Pitt movie"
 - Babylon, Fight Club, Bullet Train
 3. Movie was directed by David Fincher
 - Google David Fincher movies, use IMDB
 - Cross reference with Brad Pitt movies
 - He directed Fight Club, and Se7en, and the Curious Case of Benjamin Button.
 4. Movie also stars Edward Norton and was released in 1999

Example: continued

- The movie is Fight Club
- Song, "Where is My Mind" by The Pixies
- Citation:
 - According to the band, The Pixies, the legendary, Grammy nominated alternative rock band, in their 1988 hit song, "Where is My Mind?" played at the end of the movie, Fight Club, they say, "Your head will collapse, and there's nothing in it."
 - Red = Author Name
 - Purple = Date
 - Blue = Author Credibility
 - Green = Name of publication
 - Orange = Actual info being used to support claims

After all rounds of the movie clue activity are completed, the first level has concluded. The second level of the lesson asks students to complete a research worksheet within their groups. During this stage, students use a range of research tools, including their institution's library database, Google Scholar, and more. This step helps familiarize students with academic resources that may initially seem more complex or intimidating than a standard Google search, such as research databases and scholarly journals. Instructors may choose to award participation or extra credit points to teams that complete the worksheet first while achieving perfect accuracy. The questions can be adapted as needed to align with other institutions' databases. Both the worksheet and its answer key are provided in the appendix.

Debriefing and Appraisal

Since the incorporation of this activity into the BCC, students have showcased an ability to conduct quality research, cite sources more easily and appropriately, and integrate a greater variety of supporting materials into their speeches. In short, the result of this activity has yielded positive results related to information literacy students who have participated.

Since its inception, approximately 120 students have participated in this activity across four 10-week terms. During this time, instructor assessments indicated measurable improvement in students' ability to integrate and orally cite sources within their speeches. Informal feedback reinforces these results because many students report greater confidence in understanding how to cite information ethically during oral presentations. While these findings are preliminary and informal rather than formal statistical analysis, they provide promising evidence that the lesson contributes to the intended learning outcomes.

The limitations of this activity are minor and mostly involve students' comfort in engaging with new tools, as well as citing sources (both traditional sources and those that are not typically defined as scholarly). However, through this assignment, students get experience with both. The first level of the activity asks students to create oral citations using musicians and their songs to ensure they can develop oral citations correctly. The next level asks students to engage with various research tools, including their institution's library research database. Sometimes, these tools have never

been utilized by students before this activity. Regardless of this potential learning curve, this activity teaches multiple valuable lessons. First, students learn they have access to a plethora of valuable research tools beyond a basic Google. Second, students learn how to identify what makes a source credible and apply this to their speeches. This activity has led to more quality research being conducted, improved oral citations, and a greater variety of supporting materials being utilized by students.

Implementation Variations

While this activity is geared towards a smaller sized classroom, a number of implementation variations can occur. After all, the action of finding sources and citing them correctly is not exclusive to oral presentations. Therefore, instructors across disciplines could tailor this idea to their specific courses. For example, a professor of history could alter this lesson by utilizing movies related to historical events and adjust the second level of this process to be specific to properly citing history-related research in the correct context.

Further, instructors could work in conjunction with the librarians at their respective institutions to increase the research abilities of students. Librarians could co-teach this lesson with instructors, which could theoretically help save time during the verification process. This collaborative approach could also help students better utilize the plethora of resources college libraries offer.

This lesson can also be effectively adapted for online learning environments. During synchronous courses, instructors may use breakout rooms to facilitate group collaboration and leverage the institution's learning management system (LMS) to organize and assess student submissions. In asynchronous settings, instructors can assign a comparable activity or assignment that guides students through the same research and citation steps independently. Overall, the benefits of this lesson are transferable across multiple instructional formats and course types that emphasize high-quality research practices.

Handouts and appendices available online at www.UJOC.org/.

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